

“ETHNOM EDICINAL STUDIES OF *ACALYPHA INDICA* L
(EUPHORBIACEAE)”

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Short Profile

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ABSTRACT:

The present work deals with review of ethnobotanical uses of *Acalypha indica* L. family Euphorbiaceae is commonly known as Kupi, Khokali. The plant has been used widely by traditional practitioners for the treatment of various diseases. The Leaves, root, stalks (young shoots) and flowers are used in medicine. It has Cathartic, Anthelmintic, expectorant, emetic, anodyne and hypnotic properties. The therapeutic properties of *Acalypha* in Ayurveda and Siddha texts are discussed in detail in this article. The plants also used in the treatment of domestic animals.

KEYWORDS

Traditional uses, Acalypha, Khokali.

INTRODUCTION

Acalypha indica L. is an annual erect herb found throughout various parts of India, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, the Philippines and tropical Africa. [1] The plant has wide uses in the traditional medicines of various countries and reportedly possesses diuretic, purgative and anthelmintic properties, besides being also used for bronchitis, asthma, pneumonia, scabies and other cutaneous diseases [2] A drug used for prevention and reversal of atherosclerotic disease process in the Sidha system of Indian medicine, Anna Pavala Sindhooram, contains the leaves of this plant as one of the ingredients [3]. Chemical constituents reported from this plant include acalyphamide (as acetate), aurantiamide and its acetate, succinimide calypho-lactate, 2-methyl anthraquinone, tri-Omethylellagic acid, β -sitosterol and its β -D-glucoside (leaves); a cyanogenetic glucoside, acalyphine, two alkaloids, viz, acalyphine and triacetoneamine, an essential oil n-octacosanol, kaempferol, quebrachitol, β -sitosterol acetate and tannin (whole plant); stigmasterol (root) [4] Recently, four kaempferol glycosides, mauritianin, clitorin, nicotiflorin and biorobin have also been isolated from the flowers and leaves of this plant [5].

Acalypha indica L.(Euphorbaceae)

Acalypha indica in Ayurveda:

Preparations:

Infusion of root, powder, decoction, cataplasm, succus (juice expressed), tincture and liquid extract.

Uses:

- Leaves possess laxative properties; are used as a substitute for senega; are used in the form of powder or decoction.
- Mixed with garlic they are used as Anthelmintic in worms. Mixed with garlic they are applied to scabies; and their juice mixed with oil forms an application in rheumatic arthritis.
- Expressed juice of the leaves is a safe, certain and speedy emetic for children in one teaspoonful doses, in cases of croup; in smaller doses it is expectorant, and is useful in chronic bronchitis, asthma and consumption.
- The decoction is employed in ear-ache as instillation and also as fomentation round the aching ear; and a cataplasm of the bruised.
- Leaf paste is applied to syphilitic ulcers, to maggot-eaten sores and also to relieve the pain of snakebites.
- Juice from fresh leaves may be employed in scabies and other skin diseases, and with lime and onion it is a good stimulating application in rheumatism.
- Powder of dry leaves is used in bed sores.
- In congestive headache a piece of cotton saturated with the expressed juice of the plant or leaves and inserted into each nostril is said to relieve it by 'causing hemorrhage from the nose.
- In cases of obstinate constipation of children the leaves ground into a paste and made into a ball and introduced into the rectum, relax the sphincter ani and produces free motions.
- An infusion of the root or the root bruised in water, acts as a cathartic [6].

Acalypha indica in Siddha Medicine:

Properties: Taste (Suvai) : Bitter, Kaarpu.

Effect during digestion (Veeriyam): Kaarpu.

Post digestive taste (Pirivu): Kaarpu.

Actions: Anodyne, Anthelmintic, Cathartic, Diuretic, Expectorant, Emmenagogue, Emetic.

Therapeutic Properties:

According to the Siddha text, 'Pathartha Guna Chinthamani' (Page no:179), *Acalypha* cures diseases of the teeth and gums, burns, toxins of Plant and mixed origin, stomach pain, diseases due to Pitha, bleeding piles, irritations, stabbing pain, wheezing, sinusitis and neutralizes predominance of the Kapha factor.

According to Siddha Materia Medica [7] the leaf powder when given in the dose of 950 mg to 1300 mgs, cures respiratory diseases. The leaf juice when mixed with neem oil and applied to the inner part of children's tongue with the help of quill, induces vomiting and acts as expectorant.

When the *Acalypha* leaves in moderate, prescribed quantity is taken along with diet, it removes Thimir Vaatham from the body. When the leaves are fried up with castor oil and given in the prescribed quantity and method for 45 days (mandalam), it removes disastrous Kapha diseases, combined with Vayu (gas) and produces good health. For removing the toxin arising out of Rat bite, the leaves of *Acalypha* in the size of areca nut is mixed with water and given for 3 days (with salt restricted diet) [8]. But it produces vomiting and diarrhea also.

***Acalypha indica* in Ethno medicinal Uses:**

- Leaf paste is externally applied on lower part of abdomen for relief in spasmodic retention of urine.
- Powder of dried roots is orally given with water or milk, to cure pneumonia.
- The roots of *A. indica* is used as laxative and leaves for scabies and other cutaneous diseases.
- In the Philippines, decoction of leaves used for dysentery.
- Juice of the root and leaves given to children as expectorant and emetic.
- The leaves, in decoction or powdered form, are used as a laxative.
- For constipation, an anal suppository of the bruised leaves helps relax the constricted sphincter and muscle.
- Leaves mixed with garlic used as anthelmintic.
- Leaves mixed with common salt applied to scabies.
- Poultice of bruised leaves used for syphilitic ulcers, to maggot-eaten sores and as emollient to snake bites.
- Powdered dried leaves used for bed sores.
- Juice of fresh leaves, mixed with oil or lime, used for rheumatic complaints.
- Decoction of leaves used as instillation for earaches and for periauricular poultice or compress.
- Root, bruised in water, used as cathartic.
- Bruised leaves used as "suppository" in constipation, assumed to work through decrease of the sphincter and contraction.
- In Indian pharmacopoeia, used as an expectorant. Also used for the prevention and reversal of atherosclerotic disease. Used for pneumonia, asthma and rheumatism.
- In Tamilnadu, India, the Paliyar tribes of Shenbagathope use the entire plant for bronchitis, a decoction of the herb for tooth- and earaches and paste of the leaves applied to burns.

Clinical Studies:

- **Post-Coital Infertility Activity:** Petroleum ether and ethanol extracts of *A. indica* were found to be effective in causing significant anti-implantation activity [9].
- **Flavonoids:** Four known kaempferol glycosides—mauritianin, clitorin, nicotiflorin and biorobin were isolated from the flowers and leaves of *A. indica* [5].
- **Phytochemicals:** Studies yielded fatty acids (eicosatrienoic acid methyl ester, hexatriacontane, trimethyl undecatriene and trifluoroacetic acid), volatile essential oil (phytol), and flavonoids (naringin, quercitrin, hesperitin and kaempferol; most of the identified components having their own medicinal properties [10].
- **Antibacterial:** (1) Study has shown it to possess antibacterial activity against *Aeromonas hydrophilla* and *Bacillus cereus*. [2] All extracts of leaves of *Acalypha indica* exhibited antibacterial activity against Gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus*, *S. epidermis*, *B. cereus*, *Strep faecalis*). Among gram-negative bacterial only *P. aeruginosa* was susceptible to the extracts. [11]
- **Vasoconstrictor Activity:** Study showed the petroleum ether extract exhibited better vasoconstrictor activity against blood vessels of frog comparable to the reference drug adrenaline. Results provide support for use of the extract in treating disorders of headache and migraines, and for diuretic and alexeteric effects. [12].
- **Antioxidant:** Ethanol and aqueous extract of root of *A. indica* showed nitric oxide scavenging activity in a dose-dependent manner. [13]
- **Wound Healing:** Study showed the water extracts of *Azadirachta indica* and *Acalypha indica* were more

effective than the acetone extracts particularly on pseudomonas sp. Results suggest a potential for use in wound infections.[14]

- **Antidiabetic:** Study of methanol and acetone extract in alloxan-induced diabetic rat model showed dose-dependent antidiabetic activity attributed to an increased uptake of glucose at the tissue level or by an increase in pancreatic beta cell function or due to inhibition of intestinal absorption of glucose. [15]

- **Anti-ulcer:** Ethanol extract has an anti-ulcer property. [12]

- **Antifungal / Antimicrobial:** (1) Study of fresh, dried and powdered samples of leaf, stem and root of *Acalypha indica* showed activity against *Candida albicans*, *Aspergillus niger* and *E. coli*. An active compound showed more activity than clotrimazole. (2) Study concludes the plant has potential antifungal properties providing a scientific basis for utilization of the plant for treatment of antifungal infections. Results of study were negative for antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. [13]

- **Antimalarial:** Results of leaf extract of *A. indica* show promising larvicidal and ovicidal activity against malaria vector *A. stephensi*. [14]

- **Antidiabetic:** Study of methanol and acetone extract in alloxan-induced diabetic rat model showed dose-dependent antidiabetic activity attributed to an increased uptake of glucose at the tissue level or by an increase in pancreatic beta cell function or due to inhibition of intestinal absorption of glucose. [15]

- **Antimicrobial:** Study evaluating the antimicrobial activity of different extracts of *A. indica* showed antibacterial activity against Gram-positive bacteria was more pronounced in water and ethanol extracts and antifungal activity significant with the chloroform extract. [16]

- **Anti tuberculosis:** Study of Extracts of all the five plants *A. indica*, *A. vasica*, *A. cepa*, *A. sativum* and *A. vera* exhibited anti-tuberculosis activity in L-J medium, the proportion of inhibition of these plants of these plants showed significant inhibition against *M. tuberculosis*[17].

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